

Impact of Computerized Accounting on The Performance of Deposit Money Banks Listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange

BY

Inedu Abraham Idoko & Dr. G.M. Tyokoso. Ph.D

Department Of Accounting and Finance,

University of Agriculture, Makurdi

Benue State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The study examined the impact of computerized Accounting on the performance of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The objective of this research study is the impact of computerized Accounting on the performance of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The research employed the descriptive research design. The target population in this study comprises 8 banks which are listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange within the study period. In the course of the study, the selected banks annual reports were used to derive Return on Assets (ROA) for 5 years which is from 2014 to 2018. The data obtained were analysed using STATA version 15. The study findings indicate that Automated Teller Machine (ATM) has significant impact on the performance of selected deposit money banks listed on the NSE, Point-of-Sale has negative but significant impact on the performance of banks listed on the NSE, while Internet Banking has no significant effect on the performance of banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The study also identified factors that pose challenges to the effective application of Computerize Accounting in the banking sector such as Internet connectivity, skilled manpower; cybercrime; installation and maintenance cost; affordability of technology innovations.

KEYWORD: Computerized Accounting; Nigerian Stock Exchange; Accounting; Automated Teller Machine.

Background of the Study

The banking industry is required as a catalyst for a rapid macro-economic development of other sectors of the economy. Therefore, its stability and growth should be the priority of the stakeholders. The recent distress and acquisition in banking industry in Nigeria the been the acquisition of Skye Bank by Polaris Bank and the reform in the sector is seen as a right decision to instil public confidence in the sector. The importance of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to the growth and sustainability of banking system in Nigeria cannot be over-emphasized. Over the years, the Nigerian banking industry has undergone remarkable operational changes; from the use of tallies and registers to cutting-edge technologies such as computers, automated teller machine (ATM), point of sales (POS) among others (Omotoso, Dada, Adelowo & Siyanbola, 2012). In the past, according to Omotosho et al; (2012) time is required to consummate business transactions successfully like cheque clearing, local and international money transfers among others. This inefficiency was due to the manual approach to initiating and completing business transactions in the banking system.

In advanced economies, technology has played a key role since 1960's. The role of computer in financial world and other spheres of life cannot be over-emphasized or, be over-looked and this has made it inevitable as the whole world has been turned into a global village. But in developing countries on the

other hand, technology has relatively been poorly deployed in customer services. Nevertheless, bank even in the strategic role of technology driven services, played in the efficient and cost-effective service delivery. Investments in innovative banking technology worldwide have therefore grown exponentially in past decade. In Nigeria, deregulation of the banking industry in 1986 saw banks deploying technology as the chief competitive weapon to achieve significant market shares in the crowded banking industries (Aduba, 1997).

This brings a good decision on the other hand leads to effective performance of managerial functions which should in turn lead to the attainment of the organization's goal.

The vital ingredients for effective information apart from accuracy must also include uniformity, timeliness, reliability, clearness and must be promptly transmitted to the recipient and same time must be relevant to the area of specification. Therefore, this presentation reviews the enabling environment for technology driven bank services in making effective planning, organization and implementation of the policies of the organization. Introduction of computer networks similarly created a new banking culture that granted customer flexibility in services delivery through wider choice of transaction outlet give bank's networks of branches. Electronic banking system was an innovation into the banking industry. It was introduced to ease the problem of; Casting delay in transaction Clearing Transfer of fund Accuracy in information from one location to the other It can be seen that before the introduction of computer in the banking industry, a lot of problems were faced in processing transaction in various sections of the bank, but with computerization, all these problems have been reduced or eased off.

The performance of banks before the introduction of computers were not as impressive, Before the introduction of computers the banks operated a manual system of accounting which is the paper-based accounting system, in which journal and ledger registers, vouchers, account books are used to store, classify and analyse financial transactions of an organization. It is often used by small businessmen, such as sole proprietors, shopkeepers, etc. to maintain the record of the business transactions, due to lower cost. The manual system, though requires a greater understanding of how to book keep, can be easier to manage, once the key concepts of double entry book keeping have been learnt. The basic book keeping skills needed, once mastered, apply to all the books of account and can be applied to any business, whether you are setting up a manual accounting system for a plumber, website designer or even a book keeping business, the fundamentals are the same. A disadvantage of a

manual accounting system is the likelihood of human error; however, those errors manifest themselves. Errors in addition, transposition of figures, incorrect recording of a transaction, incomplete recording of a transaction, - where only one side of the double entry is recorded - are all quite common mistakes and can prove to be quite difficult to locate without a good deal of experience in accounting. Another obvious disadvantage is the likelihood of damage to the records themselves. It might seem an obvious downside, but the records in a paper-based accounts system are susceptible to damage by water, fire and other perils. In addition, where there exists many transactions to record in a business the sheer volume of transactions can be a disadvantage of a manual accounting system. The manual system had effect on the performance of banks before the introduction of computers; it was impossible to backup data, the system was prone to human errors, the process was slow. The role of technology in the "Information Age" is well recognized by business, industry, and government and is completely woven into their organisational structures and strategic planning processes (Omotosho et al. 2012). Businesses need to continuously find better and faster ways to adapt to the stiff competition and rapidly changing market conditions in order to compete in today's high technology and fast paced environment. Globalisation as noted by Ehikhamenor (2003)

Statement of Problem

Before the introduction of computer in banking operation, the banking industry was faced with a lot of problems that made some people to lost interest and confidence in them (banks). These problems are as follows;

1. Delay in responses and services delivery time Improper handling,
2. Storing and keeping of date and records Inaccuracy/errors in data entries and interest's computations.
3. Transmission of fund from one place to another.
4. Cash holding movement Delays in clearing cheque Poor monitoring of accounts leading to fraud which had effect on the performance of banks.

In order to eradicate or minimize all these problems, and foster confidence in banking industry, computerization was introduced to overcome all these problems and build confidence back into the industry and the people. But along the way the computerized system developed some problems which are;

1. Challenges of electronic payment system,
2. cyber-security issues,
3. challenge to maximize efficiency of bank,
4. low-cost customer-oriented services,

all these problems faced by the computerized system of accounting may have effect on the performance of banks.

Objective of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine the impact of computerized Accounting System in the performances of banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. Specifically, the objectives of this research study are as follows:

- i To examine whether the Automated Teller Machines(ATM) has effect on the performance of banks as a result of computerized Accounting System.
- ii To examine whether Point-of-Sale has effect on the performance of banks as a result of computerized Accounting System.
- iii To examine whether Internet Banking(e-Banking) has effect on the performance of banks as a result of computerized Accounting System.

Research Questions

In order to achieve the objective of this research study, the study attempts to provide answers to the following research questions

- i How has Automated Teller Machines(ATM) improved the performance of banks in the Nigerian Stock Exchange?
- ii How has the introduction of Point-of-Sale(POS) affected the performance of banks?
- iii To what extent has Internet Banking(e-Banking) affected the performance of banks in the Nigerian Stock Exchange?

Technology Innovations Deployment in the Banking Industry

Technology innovation deployment is anchored on information and communication technology (ICT). ICTs “refer to” technologies people use to share, distribute, gather information and to communicate through computers and computer networks” (Laudon and Laudon; 2001). ICTs represent a cluster of associated technologies defined by their functional usage in information access and communication, of which one embodiment is the Internet (Dauda and Akingbade, 2011).

ICT affects financial institutions by easing enquiry, saving time, and improving service delivery. In recent decades, investment in IT by commercial banks has served to streamline operations, improve competitiveness, and increase the variety and quality of services provided (Agboola, 2003; Dauda and Akingbade, 2011). ICT also offers quicker rate of inter-branch transactions as the consequence of distance and time are eliminated. Also, with the several networked branches serving the customer populace as one system, there is simulated division of labour among bank branches with its associated positive impact on productivity among the branches and curtails customer travel distance.

Technological innovation such as the use of computer automation and electronic banking influences speed of bank services delivery, enhances management decision making and time saving (Alu, 2002). Thus, Technological Innovation deals with the Physical devices and software that link various computer hardware components and transfer data from one physical location to another (Laudon and Laudon; 2001 & 2010). ICT products in use in the banking industry include Automated Teller Machine, Smart Cards, Telephone Banking, MICR, Electronic Funds Transfer, Electronic Data Interchange, Electronic Home and Office Banking. Electronic Banking has tremendously improved the services of banks to their customers (Agboola, 2001).

Technological innovations have been argued to contribute to the distribution channels of banks (Joshua, 2003). The various ICT innovations deployed in the banking sector to enhance the banking operations are as follows:

Internet Banking

Technology innovation deployment using internet banking Internet banking gives customers access to their bank accounts through a website (Essinger, 1999). Internet banking offers more convenience

and flexibility to customers with absolute control over their banking activities. In addition, it is the most cost-efficient technological means of yielding higher productivity” (Dauda and Akingbade, 2011; Omotosho et al, 2012). Internet banking allows customers to check account balances, transfer funds and apply for loans. It uses three-dimensional graphics to enable customers to move into different rooms and communicate with virtual bank tellers, loan arrangers and financial advisers. It uses visa remote banking subsidiary, visa interactive, to link banks with customers and provide secure technology for the safety of account data transferred (Agboola, 2006).

Automated Teller Machines (ATMs)

Automated Teller Machines is a combination of a computer terminal, record-keeping system and cash vault in one unit, permitting customers to enter the bank’s book keeping system with a plastic card containing a Personal Identification Number (PIN) or by punching a special code number into the computer terminal linked to the bank’s computerized records 24 hours a day (Rose, 1999). The combined services of both the Automated and human tellers imply more productivity for the bank during banking hours. Also, as it saves customers time in service delivery as alternative to queuing in bank halls, customers can invest such time saved into other productive activities. ATMs are a cost-efficient way of yielding higher productivity as they achieve higher productivity per period of time than human tellers (Dauda and Akingbade, 2011). ATM was introduced first to function as cash dispensing machines. However, due to advancement in technology, ATM has been able to provide a wide range of services, such as making deposits, funds transfer between two or more accounts and bill payments e.g. digital satellite television (DSTV). Banks tend to utilize this electronic banking device, as all other for competitive advantage (Omotoso et al., 2012)

Electronic Funds Transfer at Point of Sale (EFTPoS)

Point-of-Sale is an on-line system that allows customers to transfer funds instantaneously from their bank accounts to merchant accounts when making purchases (at purchase points). A POS uses a debit card to activate an Electronic Fund Transfer Process (Chorafas, 1988). Increased banking productivity results from the use of EFTPoS to service customers shopping payment requirements instead of clerical duties in handling cheques and cash withdrawals for shopping. Furthermore, the

system continues after banking hours, hence continual productivity for the bank even after banking hours. It also saves customers time and energy in getting to bank branches or ATMs for cash withdrawals which can be harnessed into other productive activities” (Dauda and Akingbade, 2011; Omotosho et al, 2012).

Impact of Computerized Accounting System on the Performance of Banks

The concepts of computerised Accounting system or ICT on the performance of various banks performance have transformed the entire universe into a global village. It is no sufficient to provide products, but to align these closely with specific customer segments and their identified expectations. Banking like most industries, has been transformed by technological innovations. These have made it possible to offer alternative delivery channels for services such as Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), Electronic Banking (Internet Banking), Credit and Debit Cards, and execution of payments through Electronic Funds Transfer at the point of sale (EFTPOS). While most of these have been the norm in the developed world, it is rapidly catching on in Nigeria but at varying paces for different African countries. Some other available telecommunication and information technologies which are presently being used in the banking industry in Nigeria are telephone, facsimile, wireless radiophone, very small aperture terminal satellites (VSAT), telegraphy and computer systems (Ugwu, 1999).

In his study of the Tanzanian situation, Mboma (2006), found that customers in the country found satisfaction in their use of ATM cards which also helped in their performance. In Nigeria, researchers have mainly focused on regulatory and security implications of the technology. For instance, Oghenerukeybe (2009) studied customers’ perception of security indicators in online banking sites and found that security indicators (SIs) are not effective at alerting and shielding users from revealing sensitive information to spoofed sites. This led to her recommending that banks develop effective security strategies for the future of electronic banking in Nigeria. However, research on the impact of ICT on banks’ performance is insufficient and the available studies are more of US, European and Australian banking industry. Carlson (2000) and Furst (2002) conducted an intensive research whether there is a positive relationship that exists between offering electronic banking and

bank's profitability. Furst (2002), reveals that federally chartered US banks had higher Return on Equity (ROE) by using the conventional business model, ICT was one of the major factors that affect bank's profitability within the period under study and they also observe that more profitable banks adopt ICT after 1998 but yet they are not the first movers. On the same note, Eglund (1998), conducted a study and found no evidence of major differences in performance of electronic banking in the US subject to two caveats:

1. This result may not be the case for all the banks.
2. Such results are open to change over time as banks become more severe in the use of innovation.

ICT has enhanced all performance measures which include profit, efficiency, effectiveness, productivity and quality. This has made way for organizations to enjoy the benefits listed below (Dumitru, Glavan, Dumitru & Glavan, 2010).

- **Competition:** ICT has enabled organizations to stay competitive by increasing quality and efficiency.

- **Analysis:** better detailed analysis of information can be done with the use of computer software which increases reliability.

- **Control:** management has greater control over the business with IT, as managing organizational activities has been made easy for them with less human error to worry about.

- **Direction:** ICT provides a sense of direction for organizations as they can stay up-to-date and relevant with information, identifying the right processes to take on, the ways to avoid and the most profitable means of running the firm.

- **Decision Making:** better decisions can be made with the help of ICT for the organizations as computers provide certain details which humans cannot, thereby increasing accurate decisions.

- **Identification of Business Opportunities:** from the direction provided by ICT, profitable business opportunities can be identified by the organizations.

Banks see investment in ICT as a means by which they can improve their organizational performance based on the earlier mentioned measures. Such investment has produced positive effects over subsequent periods and can be said to have increased the company's productivity and performance (Ali, Abbas & Reza, 2013).

Recommendation and Conclusion

Based on the outcome of this study, the following recommendations are advanced:

- i It is imperative for bank management to intensify investment in Automated Teller Machine (ATM) products to facilitate speed, convenience, and accurate services. These will make Nigerian banks to be efficient, profitable, and competitive and to cope with the changes and challenges.
- ii Bank should invest minimal on Point-of-Sale (POS) equipment procurement, installation, training and retraining of members of staff. This will enable the banks to update their human and other resources with best practice globally.
- iii The application of Internet Banking in the banking sector also presents its own challenges which ranges from insecurity, cybercrime and fraud which scares some customers away. These challenges can be overcome using diverse means and especially the public-private partnership on security issues and infrastructures.

This research work aims at understanding the Impact of computerized accounting on the performance of Deposit money banks listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange, how the variables interrelate, and the extent to which these identified variables impact on the banks performance. Empirical data were gathered through the annual reports and statement of accounts of the selected Deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Importance of computerized accounting is indispensable. Moreover, computerized accounting has positive impact on the performance of Deposit money banks as shown in the findings. Based on the findings, computerized accounting is significantly related to the performance of Deposit money banks in Nigeria. The findings also showed that Point-of-Sale is negatively significant to performance. The result also showed that the Internet Banking is insignificant to performance while Automated Teller Machine is significant to performance of Deposit money banks listed in Nigerian Stock Exchange.

REFERENCES

- Aduba N.C.O (1997) "Technology Driven Banking Services Hand Book Technology Driven Banking Services Hand Book Series" *Volume 10, Number 2, 1997, Pg 4. Anderson R.G.*
- Agboola, A.A. (2001). Impacts of Electronic Banking on Customer Services in Lagos, Nigeria. *Ife Journal of Economic and Finance*, 5(2), 20 -26.
- Akinuli, O.M. (1999) Information Technology in Nigeria's Banking Industry: Operational Applications, Problems and Future Challenges, *CBN Bullion*, 23(3), 71-75.
- Ali, A., Abbas, A., & Reza, A. (2013). The effect of Information Technology on Organizational Structure and Firm Performance: *An analysis of Consultant Engineers Firms (CEF) in Iran. Procedia- Social And Behavioural Sciences*, 81, 644-649. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016>.
- Chiemeké, S. C., Ewwiekpaefe, A., and Chete, F. (2006) The Adoption of Internet Banking in Nigeria: An Empirical Investigation. *Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce*, 11(3), 32 – 41.
- Dauda, Y. A and Akingbade, W.A (2011) Technology Innovation and Nigeria banks' performance: The Assessment of employee's and customer's responses. *American Journal of Social and Management Science*, 2(3), 329 – 340.
- Dumitru, V., Glăvan, E., Dumitru, M., & Glăvan, N. (2010) The Impact Of Information Technologies On The Performance Of The Financial-Accounting Department Of The Company (1st ed.). *Romania. Retrieved March 18, 2016 from <http://fse.tibiscus.ro/anale/Lucrari2010/061.%20Dumitru%20Madalina.pdf>*
- Egland, K. L., Furst, K., Nolle, D., E. and Robertson, D. (1998). "Banking over the Internet", *Quarterly Journal of Office of Comptroller of the Currency, Journal of Small Business Management*, 17 (4), 23-67.
- Ehikhamenor , F. A (2003) Information technology in Nigerian banks: The limits of expectations Information Technology for Development. *IOS Press Africa Regional Centre for Information*, 10 (1) 13–24.
- Eija, K. (2011). Theories of ICT System Implementation and Adoption – A Critical Review (1st ed.). Finland. Retrieved from http://lib.tkk.fi/SCIENCE_TECHNOLOGY/2011/isbn9789526041506.pdf.
- Essinger, J.(1999) *The virtual Banking Revolution: The customer, the Bank and the Future.* (1st ed.) London: International Thomson Business press.
- Francis, P. (2013). Impact of Information Technology on Accounting Systems. *Asia-Pacific Journal Of Multimedia Services Convergent With Art, Humanities, And Sociology*, 3(2), 93-106. <http://dx.doi.org/10.14257>.
- Idowu, P.A., Alu, A.O and Adagunodo, E.R (2002) The Effect of Information Technology on the growth of the banking industry in Nigeria" *Electronic Journal of Information System in Developing Countries*, 10(2), 1 – 8.
- Kaushik, P. D. and N. Singh. (2004) Information Technology and Broad-Based Development: Preliminary Lessons from North India. *World Development*, 32, 591- 607.
- Laudon, D.P. and J.P. Laudon(2001) *Management Information Systems: Organisation and Technology in the Network Enterprises*, 4th ed. New York: Prentice Hall International.
- Linus, P. (2012). UPA FOREX AND ICT: The impact of ICT on accounting practice in Nigeria. Retrieved from <http://linexupah.blogspot.com.ng/2012/09/the-impact-of-ict-on-accounting.html>.
- Mboma, L.M (2006), ATM and customer satisfaction: A case of the banking industry in Tanzania, *The African Journal Finance and Management*, 15(1) pp 48-70.
- National Bureau of Statistics. *Annual Abstract of Statistics*, 2011.

- Obasan, K.A. (2011) "Information and communication technology and banks profitability in Nigeria". *Australian Journal of Business and Management Research* 1(4) 102-107.
- Oghenerukeybe, E.A (2009), Customers perception of security indicators in online banking sites in Nigeria, *Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce*, 14(1), <http://www.arraydev.com/commerce/jibc>.
- Oluwagbemi, O., Abah, J., and Achimugu, P. (2011) The Impact of Information Technology in Nigeria's Banking Industry. *Journal Of Computer Science And Engineering*, 7(2). 63- 69.
- Omotoso, K. O., Dada, A.D., Adelowo, C.M and Siyanbola, W.O (2012) Linking Innovations with Productivity in Nigeria Banking firm: What roles for ICT? *Management Journal*, 2(5), 204 – 213.
- Ovia, J. (2005), Enhancing the Efficiency of the Payment System in Nigeria, *CBN Bullion*, 29 (1),8-18.
- Rose, P. S.(1999) *Commercial banking management*, (4ed.) Boston, Irwin/McGraw-Hill, Uk.
- Salawu R. O. and Salawu M. K. (2007) The emergence of internet banking in Nigeria: an appraisal, *Information Technology Journal*, Vol. 6(4), pp 490 – 496.
- Shrivastava, P. (1984) "Technology Innovation in Developing Countries, USA". *Columbia Journal of World Business*, winter, 23-28.
- Stamoulis, D. ,(2006) How Banks Fit in an Internet Commerce Business Activities Model. *Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce*, 5(1) 35- 43.
- Taylor, O.W (1958) Variables related to creativity and productivity among men in two research Laboratories, *University of Utah creativity Research Report*.
- Ugwu, L.O. , Oyebisi, T.O. , Ilori, M.O. and Adagunodo, E.R. (2000)"Organizational Impact of Information Technology on Banking and Insurance Sector in Nigeria". *Technovation* 20(12), 66 - 73.
- Woherem, E.W. (2000): *Information Technology in the Nigerian Banking Industry*. Ibadan: Spectrum Books.